

**DID THE PANDEMIC REVIVE
THE “FACEBOOK REVOLUTION” IN MOROCCO?
HYBRID SPACES AND FORMS OF POLITICAL ENGAGEMENT AFTER 2011**

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Introduction

The year 2020-2021 has seen the explosion of the Coronavirus pandemic that caused massive consequences on the health, economic and political level worldwide. One of the numerous regulations put in place around the world to contain the virus was to limit or deny the access to public space for many millions of people, who have therefore oriented themselves into a massive use of the Internet to try to cope with this crisis. The year 2020-2021 also coincided with the ten-year recurrence of the beginning of the so-called “Arab Springs”, an umbrella term – often criticized – used to define the set of revolts, uprisings and armed rebellions that have crossed many countries of North Africa and the Middle East between 2010 and 2012. During this period, the Internet and the then fledgling social networking platforms, such as Facebook or YouTube, played a crucial role in reporting, diffusing and sometimes organizing popular discontent.

As happened for the wave of protests that took place between 2010 and 2012 in several countries of the Arab World, also the 2011 mobilizations in Morocco were marked by the massive use of social media platforms, not only to visibilize mobilizations, but also to destabilize them. Several researches conducted regarding the use of the Internet and political activism (Della Porta 2014; Gerbaudo 2015) especially with regard to the Arab world (Amar and Prashad 2013; Faris 2013; Khamis 2013; Mohamed, Douai, and Iskandar 2019), have highlighted how the emergence of online activism has largely influenced the practices of collective action, especially among the younger generations. Morocco is also no exception (Najar 2013; Merolla and Dahraoui, 2017; Laouni 2020; Chaaibat 2020).

However, although platforms such as Facebook, YouTube or Twitter have played an important role in redefining the spaces, practices and representations of protests, it would be inaccurate to reduce the analysis to dichotomies such as public-private or online-offline. In this sense, the exponential and sudden increase in the use of the Internet after the Coronavirus restrictions can give us insights regarding the changes occurred in Moroccan digital and non-digital activism in the last decade. Thus, this study aims at examine the unprecedented challenges that the pandemic is posing to political engagement and political socialization in contemporary Morocco by looking at the hybrid forms that this activism is taking, also in the light of the legacy left by the digital activism of 2011.

This paper is based on an ethnography centered in Morocco around student groups close to the 20 February movement, central actor of the “Moroccan spring”. The research, initiated in 2016 in two universities of north-western Morocco (Meknes and Kenitra),

continues today with an online ethnography of the Facebook activities conducted by the groups active in those same universities. For these student groups, the university campus was a space for acquiring and sharing practices and discourses that were otherwise prohibited in other places of their daily lives (the street or their family homes). However, the limitations caused by the pandemic have led the groups to move their activities almost exclusively to the online sphere. Thus, I address the following questions: How the hybridization of spaces and practices can inform us on the ways in which form of self-expression and political engagement are performed inside and outside the Internet? What is the legacy of the 2011 digital activism in these hybrid forms of engagement? Does the collective memory of 2011 play a role in transmitting or redefining the groups' practices? Do the restrictions to the public space open the way to new modes of communication and spaces of aggregation? Or do they favor their control by the State?

The study case presented here derived from a qualitative ethnographic research of the online and offline spaces, practices and discourses of the student groups' activism. This qualitative analysis has been guided by the following consideration: in order to overcome methodological difficulties of observing a hybrid activism, constantly traversing online and offline spheres, it has been important to adapt the research tools. Therefore, I have followed a multimodal ethnographic approach (Beneito-Montagut 2011; Hine 2015), by constituting a set of material and methods which involve the use of both qualitative tools of the anthropological tradition and quantitative methods coming from the field of Digital Humanities. Thus, with regard to offline fieldwork, qualitative research was conducted through participant observation and semi-structured qualitative interviews. To understand the socio-spatial inscription of student activists in the university campus, I have resorted to some tools of the method of the "cognitive cartography" (Felonneau 1994). As far as online analysis is concerned, qualitative research techniques – based on online interviews and monitoring of virtual events – have been combined with quantitative analyses such as the web scraping of Facebook groups and pages and YouTube channels thanks to the use of programming languages such as Python. This in order to collect quantitative data about recurrent topics, different language uses, but also number and gender of the participants.

The argument raised here is that, even if the restriction caused by the pandemic have encouraged an exponential and near-exclusive use of the Internet regarding to activism, this also seems to have accentuated social inequalities and thus contributed to questioning the democratizing image of the Internet, very much widespread during the waves of mobilizations occurring in many Arab majority countries between 2010 and 2012. Moreover,

if we consider Morocco's political context of the last decade, we can notice that, contrary to other coercive strategies put in place after 2011, the one pursued by Moroccan government implied both the repression and the cooptation of anti-regime movements, including digital activism. By addressing such topics, this study aims at providing valuable insights into Morocco's hybrid forms of youth political socialization, emphasizing the importance of observing political phenomena from an ethnographic and contextualized approach.

Thus, the article is organized in three sections: firstly, I will provide with an historical contextualization of Morocco during the uprisings of 2011 and I will introduce the actors involved and their spaces of action before and after the pandemic. Secondly, I will delve into offline and online ethnographic studies of the groups' practices to examine how the digital sphere may have helped to reshape the activism of the social actors involved in this study. Finally, I will propose a reflection concerning the changes occurred in the student groups' activities during the lockdown of 2020, arguing that the use of the Internet for political engagement has been predominantly pragmatic and contingent on the pandemic situation.

Moroccan university activism during and after 2011

Historical contextualization of 2011's protests in Morocco

The mobilizations occurred in Morocco from 2011 which channeled into the heterogeneous 20 February movement (hereinafter 20FM), arrive in the country after a long economic stagnation and the impositions of the World Bank and International Monetary Fund, a structural crisis of the employment and after unexpected expectations of political and social reforms that King Mohamed VI had promised to introduce after years of political and social repression that had characterized the reign of his father, Hassan II (Maddy-Weitzman and Zisenwine 2013). However, if the internal discontent was already very diffused in Morocco, the increasingly frequent protests in other countries of the area, like Tunisia or Egypt, favored the emergence of demonstrations. While mainstream media seemed to ignore the protests, satellite channels, web press and especially social networks were diffusing audio-visual and textual material about the uprisings happening in Tunisia, Egypt, Yemen, Syria and so on. Platforms like Facebook, Twitter and YouTube thus become the primary means of communication for the creation, organization and mobilization of protest, by determining the composition of the social movement: indeed, the heterogeneous composition

of the 20FM brought together the participation of all kinds of political actors: people without political affiliation, associative organizations, members of opposing parties, political student groups (Desrues 2012a).

If this diversity has favored relative success in the implementation of certain demands, the State's response has also been effective. In this sense, contrary to other coercive strategies put in place by other countries to contrast 2011 uprisings, the one pursued by the Moroccan regime implied both the cooptation, the repression and the surveillance of the movement's actors (Emperador Badimon 2011; Hoffmann and König 2013). Finally, in order to show his availability to listen to certain demands, the king proposes a reform of the Constitution, but refused the democratic election of a constituent assembly, underscoring the desire to preserve his powers (Maghraoui 2011). However, the experience of the 20FM, proved the emergence of forms of action that criticized the classical intermediation structures such as the parties or the unions and that were not centered into overthrow the regime in place but to reclaim the implementation of policies aimed at democratizing the system, which has enlarged the range of participants in the Moroccan political public space (Vairel 2013; Kohstall 2014).

Student activism at the University

The socio-political context just described was the environment in which some of the social actors involved in this research were politically formed, while others – having started their engagement after 2015 – have politically grown up through the collective memory of the 20FM and the Arab Uprisings. However, all my interlocutors were university students and thus started their activism during high school or directly at the university, all of them joining the main Moroccan student union: the “National Union of Moroccan Students” (UNEM). Founded in 1958, after the independence of Morocco from the French protectorate, the UNEM has undergone many changes and today its influence in the Moroccan political landscape has drastically decreased (Landucci 2019). However, the union still has strong traction within Moroccan universities and its leadership is constantly disputed by different factions: there are groups displaying an “Islamist” affiliation, other following a “Marxists” ideology and others supporting the “Amazigh cause”.

Through a study conducted among the faculty and administrative staff of the university (*Ibid.* 2018), it emerged that all these factions seem to be marginalized due to the several violent clashes that occurs within the different groups. Also, there is a general idea

that the new generation of activists is unable to continue the task of social renewal assigned to the older generation of militants, the one from the 1970s. However, especially groups related to the so called “reformist Islamism” – which are today at the head of the UNEM – can count on many activists and sympathizers, but also on financial and strategic support coming from outside the university. In fact, the qualitative surveys conducted have shown that being involved in the activism of these groups, represents, among other things, an important social lift for many young Moroccans: the groups have close contacts with members of other organizations that work for the social and/or professional advancement of their members, for example the Unemployed Graduate movement (in French, *diplômés-chômeurs*) or the Moroccan Association of Human Rights (AMDH) (Emperador Badimon and Bogaert 2014), which has been a crucial actor during the protests of 2011. This social lift is especially important if we consider that all the interlocutors, aged from 20 to 35, came from the rural areas of Central Morocco and constituted the first generation to have access to the university, and therefore to the urban space.

Spaces of youth political action before and after the pandemic

The university space has also another value for these activists. Since in Morocco all political demonstration suspicious of putting into question the legitimacy of the State, and thus the Palace, is illegal, all the student groups have to militate inside the university campus. In fact, political action, especially that of young people, is subject to an extensive repressive control by the Moroccan regime, as well as the spaces in which to contest normative frameworks (i.e. related to class, origins, gender and so on) (Bennani-Chraïbi 2007; Gillot 2015; Cheikh 2020). This is also the case for student union activism, if we consider also that UNEM was declared anti-systemic and banned for 5 years from 1973 to 1978. However, as long as the union political action stays inside the university campuses it is implicitly tolerated. This shows that, when youth political activity is closely monitored by the State, the university space – even if it still reflects an institutional authority – can be a safe space for politicization of youth’s activities. The university space thus become a safe space but also a privileged environment for the politicization of youth’s activities more than other public places, like the street. Organized in large campuses far from the city centers with dormitories, cafeterias and canteens, the universities offer to the students “interstitial spaces”, between the private and the public, for organizing their collective action while being protected from the repression of the regime (Landucci 2019). On the contrary, the use of the Internet for political

engagement was looked with more distrust by many activists interviewed on the matter, due to the fear of massive surveillance. Many of them used Facebook or instant messaging platforms like Telegram – which is considered safer than WhatsApp – only as a medium to reach their “comrades” or “brothers and sisters”¹, or to exchange general information about the activities. In this sense, the experience of the digital activism of the 20FM was usually mentioned as an experience that had negative results for the success of the movement. The activists in fact underlined how “the traitors of the movement” had managed to weaken it by infiltrating the media supporting to the protests, as it happened to the website of the 20FM *Mamfakinch.com*².

During 2020, the impossibility to access the university space transformed the use of the Internet from being an option to becoming an urgent priority to ensure the very existence of the student groups: since organizing or contributing to the activities is essential for keeping the groups running, but also a crucial part of the process that allows and facilitates the change of the activists’ social conditions, it was important for the activists to find ways to carry out these activities even during the lockdown. Looking at the Internet became the only choice. In qualitative interviews conducted online during 2020-2021 with the same interlocutors, the period of digital activism of the 20FM was evoked this time as an example to follow. In fact, during the rigid confinement happened in Morocco between spring and summer 2020, almost all the activities that used to take place offline within the university campus have been moved online. In the following section I delve into the ethnographic descriptions of some of these activities that have taken place before and after the pandemic, in order to understand if and how the Internet might have reshaped them³.

¹ The expression “comrade” is used by the groups belonging to the Marxist factions while those of “brother” or “sister” are used by the Islamist factions.

² In mid-2012, a hacker attack hit the computer of some of the website’s collaborators, intercepting and stealing their files, mails and skype conversations. Even though the source was never discovered, the technology used in this hacker attack had a considerable cost and was the same usually used by the governments in crime investigations. This led to the assumption that the Moroccan government and secret services were involved in the event. In 2014 *Mamfakinch* stopped its activities by releasing a communication concerning the reasons of this interruption; see: <https://web.archive.org/web/20160324145439/https://www.mamfakinch.com/>.

³ Since ethnographic research is mainly interested in the long-term observation specific socio-cultural contexts, it should be noted that the study presented here was mainly conducted in two university cities in central Morocco (Meknès and Kenitra), but further monitoring was also done in other cities of southern and northern Morocco.

Political engagement inside and outside the Internet

The participatory mapping of the social space of the university campus conducted along with some activists of the student groups, has revealed that the university space is visited by its users in variable ways, according to a time-frame specific to the academic activities, but the practices and representations included in it go beyond the academic routine (Landucci 2019). University campuses are generally enclosed within a walled perimeter where various buildings (libraries, classrooms, professors' rooms, cafeterias) wind their way along a path of pergola corridors, small gardens and shady squares. It is in these places that student groups carry out almost all of their activities. The campus is therefore constantly rechapted, re-appropriated and contested by different political groups, who compete to earn the best place to display their posters, hold their meetings and organize their events during the academic year. Although, the groups show very different political affiliations, the activities they organize all follow routines, practices and aesthetic which are very similar between them: each group creates posters regarding the goals of the groups to hang in the corridors of the campus; every week – usually on Friday – meetings are organized in the outdoor spaces of the campus; finally, on the occasion of important anniversaries, special events called “cultural days” are held. The latter are the very core of the group’s political activities.

Cultural days or make student activism visible

Organized inside the campuses, the cultural days (in Arabic *ayyam taqafiyya*) are characterized by several days⁴, where the activists organize conferences, assemblies and interventions with external guests. The cultural aspect of these initiatives is conferred by festive moments – music concerts, poetry readings, theater improvisations – normally organized at the end of the weekly activity. Cultural days are usually held once or twice during the academic year and often in conjunction with important commemorations, such as the anniversary of the foundation of the group or the commemoration of the death of an activist⁵. In view of the symbolic preponderance of this commemoration, the choice of the

⁴ Normally from Monday to Friday, according to the university calendar.

⁵ Due to the high level of conflict between the student groups, violent clashes are not unusual and some of these led to the killing of some activists, <http://www.rssi-rabat.ma/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Violence-en-milieu-Universitaire-au-Maroc.pdf>.

university hosting the event is established according to the popularity and numerical strength of its group, and members of sections from other universities are invited to participate as delegates. Finally, these events end up being also appreciated by the academic staff that often grants spaces of the campus such as the lecture hall or the cafeteria to host the events, claiming that they prefer student union groups to “organize cultural events rather than political riots”⁶.

Among the several activities organized during the cultural days, the *halqa* is the most recurrent. When we speak of *halqa*, we are referring to forms taken by religious discussions, but also to certain styles of traditional theater in Morocco, an open-air performance performed in the squares of towns and villages ⁷. Today, the *halqa* is a circle of discussion – diffused in the squares of villages and towns or near historical centers of Moroccan big cities – in which participants can interact with the storyteller, the *hlaīqya*, around contingent issues of personal or community life. The *halqa* is also employed by student groups that use it as the standard framework in which public discussion must take place. As in the traditional *halqa*, these circles of discussions must follow specific rules of expression which recall, in a certain sense, the rhetorical forms of traditional tales told by the *hlaīqya*. For this, the place where a *halqa* takes place is just as important as the themes that are debated in it: the discussion circle will have a better chance of being followed if it is located in a place of the campus that is more frequented by students. Since *halqa* is one of the main means of recruiting new members, space therefore becomes a mobilization issue for groups competing for the most coveted areas of the campus. However, for the activists debating topics during the *halqa* is not a simple expression of adhering to an ideology: as a social event, the *halqa* allow to test the social competences and communicative skills that activists have to acquire. Being interweaved on the matter, many activists spoke of the *halqa* as a “testing arena” where to learn to “speak without taboo” or as “a chance to get out of the shadows”. Finally, speaking during an *halqa* and, generally, being actively involved into the cultural days also can give the opportunity to weave important social-links. For examples, many of the activist interviewed, and especially those who occupied higher positions inside the hierarchy of the groups, had close contacts with members of other organizations that work for the social and

⁶ In the interviews with the teaching staff, it also emerged that several professors had taken part in the student groups during their university years.

⁷ Coming from Berber oral culture, the *halqa* is made up of a circle of people formed around a storyteller, the *hlaīqya*, who generally recounts traditional Arab or Berber legends or myths.

professional advancement of its members, for example the “Unemployed graduates” movement, the *diplômés-chômeurs*.

Cultural days *go online*

As we previously seen, the construction of a social space (the campus) that could safely encourage political socialization as well as the visibilization of youth activism through individual and collective performances (the cultural days), seemed constituted the core of the political activities of the groups and thus played a crucial role for their very existence. However, the arrival of the Coronavirus disease and the subsequently lockdown suddenly forced to shut down every activity involving face-to-face social interactions, and the events organized by the student groups were no exception. Furthermore, the quarantine period in Morocco, coincided with a time normally very dense of activities for some groups, like the celebration of the Ramadan. Thus, also student group were more or less constrained to move their activities into the digital sphere if they wanted to keep their activities scheduled. Having observed their interactions online since the beginning of April 2020 until June 2020, I have noticed that all the different political factions managed to articulate their activism online, mainly in their Facebook pages, and some of them in their Twitter accounts. In some cases, and most probably for the very first time since the formation of the student groups, even the cultural days were reconfigured into the social media platforms, thanks to features like live streaming or videoconference platforms.

By observing these appointments, I have noticed that the content of the cultural days wasn't changed much, however the framework in which they were taking place forced the activists to reconfigure some practices. This is the case for the *halqa* performed online. Normally, an in-presence *halqa* would start with the groups' slogans singed firstly by the leaders then repeated by the whole group. To ensure full participation, the leaders arrange themselves equidistant from each other and slightly outside the circle, to better control the participants. The initial slogans of a *halqa* must be well executed to intrigue whoever is passing by the campus and give the public the feeling of a united group and large in number. Then, a first person gives a speech (usually the first speakers are the group leaders), and whoever wants can respond, in order to open a debate. In this regard, we have to notice that rhetoric skills are highly evaluated during in-presence *halqa*, even more that the content of the speech itself. This dimension of the oratory practice as a demonstration of capacity, but also of charisma and determination, gives rise to a real transformation in the relations

between the members of the group: those who can show to master these skills are more likely to acquiring honour and prestige within the group and thus to obtaining higher status in the internal hierarchy of the groups.

This framework, strictly linked to the spatiality of the performance, was consistently readjusted in on-line *halqa*: since the halqa was streamed in videoconference platform or Facebook live-streamed videos, the special and non-verbal character of this form of political action was replaced by the predominance of the forms of interaction. Thus, especially during Facebook live-stream videos, text-based and image-based live comments have emerged as new ways of engaging in the *halqa*. Notably, live comments seem the privileged instrument the public have to interact with the speakers/activists: while during the offline *halqa* the public had the possibility to speak in the middle of the circle and then receive an answer, during the online *halqa* live comments seem to have taken the place of the oral debate. This shift affects the *halqa* in several ways: firstly, because of Facebook live streaming's parameters allow the public to take part to the meeting just with written comments, the speakers/activist cannot engage in a debate with the creators of the comments, but just reply to them by reading the messages. Secondly, the comments stay public during and after the duration of the live streaming meeting, allowing the creation of multiple sub-debates within the public. Thirdly, non-verbal practices, like emoji or stickers, are massively used during the live streaming. Finally, since the live streaming are public, the catchment area of online *halqa* goes beyond the student population. In general, these written practices have transformed *halqa*, which is a predominantly oral performance.

Political distancing: reconfiguring student activism in times of pandemic.

The comparative examples of the online/offline *cultural days* shown in the previous section, allow us to deepen the reflection around the legacy left by the mobilizations of 2011 in Morocco and the role played by cyberactivism in the reconfiguration of the forms of engagement proper to student activism, also in the light of the social and spatial restrictions that the pandemic crisis has been caused. In this regard, the example of the offline *cultural days* shows that student groups have inherited a type of activism that is closely linked to the forms of political engagement that resulted after 2011 and the subsequent repression of its mobilizations; they have then reconfigured these forms in accordance with the daily spaces that activists cross. In fact,

if on the one hand the 20FM has managed to redefine and expand the forms taken by the protest in Morocco, on the other hand the sudden repression of this movement by the Moroccan regime has led to a shift towards activism less focused on direct confrontation with the state. So, activism after 2011 focused more on political engagement of the associative, artistic and cultural type, as it was deemed less at risk of being repressed by the state. Student group activists are also inheritors of this type of activism, whose spaces and practices shows the willingness to circumvent and not confront the state repression (i.e. the groups militate only inside the campus and promote only cultural and social activities rather than an activism in direct confrontation with the university institution).

Thus, this constraint influences the type of activism carried out by the student groups, which mainly focuses on an appropriation of the university through practices of visibilisation of the groups, as the example of the offline *halqa* have shown. This type of political engagement allows the activist, firstly, to circumvent state authority prohibitions; secondly to display a positive and engaged representation of the groups vis-à-vis the university community; and, above all, promotes the creation of a safe space that allows young people to display different lifestyles, while remaining in compliance with social norms. However, with the arrival of confinement in Morocco in the spring of 2020, this type of activism, intrinsically linked to space, encountered major upheavals. Even if we observed no discontinuities in the kind of events organized in the groups' Facebook pages, nonetheless there has been a spatial and temporal reframing that reshaped the way groups interact: one of the examples of this shifting is in the *halqa* the passage from a predominantly oral form of communication to new digitally mediated forms of interactions that mainly involve text-based and image-based communications. From a traditional oral form of speech, *halqa* has been re-appropriated by young activists to perform their political legitimacy. Today, by entering the online sphere, *halqa* might be shaped with new codes that follows the communication rules of an interactive space such as the Internet.

Streaming the past: the use of the collective memory in digital activism

However, while Internet mediated communities certainly contributed to reshaped the activists' interactions, I argue that this shift did not implied a complete reconfiguration of their political engagement which stay still very much related to a spatial engagement. Among the Facebook live videos of the online *cultural days*, there were several that show recordings that had been taken during offline events within the campus. In general, the content of these

recordings was related to symbolic moments for the student groups, for example showing the activists singing slogans and songs in memorial of their companions who died during violent clashes within the groups. The interesting aspect of these recordings is that they have been broadcasted in “live” mode and received live comment and reactions such as like and other emojis, as it would be for the online events organized during the period of lockdown. Now, these recordings refer to activities implemented in the university space before the confinement. The aim of these videos seems therefore to permanently reactivate the collective memory around a type of activism that is linked to the social and, above all, the spatial forms that activists’ lives take within the university campus. In fact, the example of streaming offline recorded videos in the Facebook online space show how the Internet, and in particular social networks, are perceived by student groups not as a new space for political socialization, but as an instrument to strengthen forms of activism already consolidated in the socio-spatial context of the university campus. In this sense, the space of the university campus, is still perceived by the group as their main instrument of visibility, because it promotes the diffusion of the routines and common representations that are essential to the maintain of the very existence of the student groups.

Conclusions

In this article, aimed at exploring the reconfigurations of Moroccan university activism after 2011 and in times pandemic. As several authors (Desrues 2012b; Vacchiano and Afailal 2019; Schwarz 2019; Borrillo 2021) have highlighted, the mobilization of the 20FM occurred in Morocco during 2011 have led to a potential for change in terms of the political actors involved, the types of claims, the spaces of contention and also the forms of political engagement. The university activism after 2011 was marked by the modes of engagement emerged during the experience of the 20FM, but also by the wave of repression and cooptation carried on by the Moroccan regime. In this regard, while the unconventional forms of mobilization promoted by the 20FM – namely the use of Internet and social media platform to diffuse the mobilizations – also reached the activists of the student groups, they did not really inherit forms of cyberactivism born in Morocco in 2011, which moreover were largely marginal compared to those emerged in Tunisia or Egypt in the same period (Lecomte 2013; Herrera 2014). Even if the lockdown derived from the pandemic crisis of 2020-2021

forced the student groups to move their activities entirely online, they still reconfigured their forms of political engagement according to strategies that allowed them to consolidate their preexistent activism instead of adapt them to the context of the Internet.

However, the ethnographic example presented here have shown that the pandemic context could have reshaped the groups' modes of interaction, as it has been observed in the transition from a mainly oral interaction to a digital textual and visual interaction as is the case of Facebook live-streamed videos of the *cultural days*. In this regard, further researches are needed concerning the reconfiguration of these practices in the context of the deconfinement from the restriction caused by the Coronavirus pandemic. On an epistemological level, the example of student groups encourages us to think of the relation between digital media and political activism as historically and socially situated in opposition to the common assumption that communication and information technologies are universally acquired and used (Khamis 2013). Finally, the reconfigurations of university activism in contemporary Morocco show us the ways in which social actors renegotiate certain cultural and social codes within but also outside the Internet, by intending the digital sphere as a set of crossings and not borders.

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